

Interview with Bkub Ōkawa at FicZone 2026

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Absurd humour takes many forms within Japanese popular culture, but few creators have achieved the international impact of **Bkub Okawa** —大川ぶくぶ. The author of *Pop Team Epic*, a manga that became a genuine publishing phenomenon and later one of the most talked-about anime adaptations in recent years, visited Granada as a guest of honour at FicZone 2026. During the event, we had the opportunity to meet him in person, alongside Kazuki Yao.

Ōkawa masterfully combines humour ranging from pure slapstick and metatextual references to satire and homages to various popular works, alongside criticism of different cultural industries, revealing a sharp intellect behind the apparent simplicity of his comic strips. His usual storytelling format is the *yonkoma*, a type of manga in which pages are typically divided into two columns —one story per column— of four panels arranged vertically —although other layouts are also possible.

Taking advantage of his stay in Spain, CoolJapan.es had the opportunity to speak with him about his professional career, his creative process, and the way he conceives a work that has managed to connect with readers and viewers around the world. Japanese humour can often feel disorientating to those encountering it for the first time. This is precisely where this author's achievement lies: he has managed to create jokes that are understood by audiences across the globe.

If there is one thing Ōkawa excels at, it is breaking conventions and turning unpredictability into his primary narrative tool, a trait that has helped cement his career as a creator.

During his conversation with CoolJapan.es, we discussed his influences, the origins of some of his more surreal ideas, the reception of his work, and his experience as an author. The result was an interview that was as engaging as it was unpredictable, reflecting the personality of an artist who has made breaking expectations one of his defining traits.

Interview with Bkub Ōkawa

Cool Japan: How would you make *Pop Team Epic* so absurd that no one within the manga world itself could explain it?

Bkub Ōkawa: [Laughs] I'd try to do it through something absurd, a parody. Something I wouldn't even try to understand myself. I'd try something... and see what happens.

A page from the first volume of the *Pop Team Epic* manga, published in Spain by Fandogamia.

CJ: What is the most ridiculous joke you've ever made that you're most proud of?

BŌ: There are many examples, but the one that immediately comes to mind is this... In some video games there's a character you control and a companion character.

Both travel through the same stage.

The companion character is programmed to automatically follow the protagonist and mimic their actions.

When the protagonist climbs stairs or something similar, the companion might get stuck on them or fall off.

So the two are walking together, but one gets trapped in a corner or keeps trying to move, stuck in front of an obstacle, while the other keeps moving further and further away. I really like that [laughs].

In *Pop Team Epic*, I adapted that situation by having Pipimi follow Popuko, but the sun blinded her and Pipimi bumped into a pillar... so Popuko kept walking away because of that! [Laughs] I love it!

CJ: How do you come up with ideas like that, so stupid they're perfect?

BŌ: Do you mean where ideas like that come from?

I think, in the end, they come from my own experiences. I parody them in a fun or comedic way in my works.

Even in the example I just gave about video games, defeats and that kind of thing—you play those games and then you keep remembering them for years in a funny or amusing way.

Or those conversations with friends where, looking back, you think: “How could I possibly have said something so absurd?”

Originally... well, these two characters [Popuko and Pipimi] probably shouldn't behave like that in the first place, but there's this sense that raising the middle finger almost becomes a form of communication... and that reminds me of an experience I had with a friend. We were playing *Super Smash Bros*. At one point I went to the bathroom, and when I came back I thought: “What would this guy think if I came back without saying anything and just gave him the middle finger?”

And when I did it, he burst out laughing and said, “Why are you flipping me off?”

So we both ended up laughing about the middle finger thing [laughs]. I suppose these kinds of funny, pleasant memories... that's where the best gags come from.

Here we can see two vinyl figures of Popuko and Pipimi produced by Hobby Max, performing their iconic gesture of showing the middle finger with both hands.

CJ: What reactions do publishers have to your work?

BŌ: [Laughs] Even when someone tells me “This is incredible” or “this is very interesting”... there are always people from different places who tell me very different things.

There are basically two types of reactions [thoughtful]. One is the idea that what I do should function almost like an academy, something that can serve other creators, and the other is rejection.

Sometimes they say things like: “We could never publish something like this at our publishing house. We had discussed working with you, but... if this is the kind of thing you write, let’s drop it.”

And they turn me down.

But other times, there are those who say: “We’d like to train an author capable of creating a work that could become our flagship title. What is your creative process like? How do you build your works?” And they show a lot of interest.

So both things happen. Since I no longer know whether they appreciate me or hate me, I don’t really mind [laughs].

CJ: If you could choose a chapter in which you parodied a video game, which would it be?

BŌ: [Thoughtful] The one that had the biggest impact and received the most comments was...

There’s a series of video games called *Super Robot Wars*. In them, famous Japanese robots [mechas] from series such as *Mazinger Z*, *Gundam* and *Getter Robo* appear together to fight against an evil organisation.

Popuko becomes the pilot of Pipimi’s mecha version: Super Pipimi. This occurs in the first half of the *Pop Team Epic* TV special broadcast in 2019, and also in the same year in the video game *Super Robot Wars X-Ω* (2015–2021), making Ōkawa the recipient of a tribute from the very series of games he had previously parodied.

They’re games that Japanese anime fans absolutely love. Today, the series is known for its spectacular animations and flashy action scenes... but in its early days it had a very particular feature: there were practically no animations [laughs].

For example, a robot would sort of move forward, attack, and return to its position, but everything was represented in a very simple way.

So I made a joke about it, saying something like: “Technology has advanced so much that it’s hard to believe there was a time when it used to be like this,” [makes robotic gestures to explain] and I gently poked fun at those times in an affectionate way...

And the fans of those games really liked it. Apparently, even the series’ producer saw it and thought it was funny.

That made me very happy.

CJ: Which famous anime character would be funniest if they appeared alongside Popuko or Pipimi?

BŌ: [Laughs] So, like some kind of showdown or crossover?

Sazae-san!

[Referring to the legendary manga *Sazae-san*, starring Sazae Isono/Fuguta; created by manga artist Machiko Hasegawa, considered the first female manga author. The anime adaptation is still ongoing, since 1969, with over 9,000 episodes.]

I can imagine her inside the series, or in a video game, or in a combat situation [laughs while making fist-fighting gestures].

I love *Sazae-san* [laughs].

CJ: Is there any joke that was censored, or that you yourself thought: “no, this is too much even for me” and decided not to use?

BŌ: When something happens that annoys me or makes me angry, sometimes I think about turning it directly into a manga.

But then, when I calm down and look at it with perspective, I realise the reader might end up absorbing that anger too.

And although manga is a form of personal expression, what I most want is to make people laugh and help them feel happy.

That’s why I try not to burden my work with overly personal messages.

CJ: If you had to define *Pop Team Epic* in one sentence for a Spanish reader... what would it be?

BŌ: [Laughs] “Don’t get angry!”

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Bkub Ōkawa for granting us one of the most entertaining interviews ever conducted for CoolJapan.es. He is exactly the kind of person you would imagine capable of creating a work as wild and original as *Pop Team Epic*. A true connoisseur of video games, manga and anime, he demonstrates a genuine closeness between mangaka and fans of his work.

It is worth highlighting the author’s remarkable dedication, who, under the relentless Andalusian sun, and despite wearing his iconic mask at all times in front of attendees—only removing it briefly for the interviews—went out of his way to engage with fans and our team, always with great energy and passion for his work.

Once again, we would like to thank the FicZone press team, especially Eladia Gómez and the Crossover organisation, as well as FicZone director Nacho Cabrero, for making the event and this interview possible.

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We would also like to thank Antonio Jiménez, from Supermercado del Juguete, who helped our colleague Andrés with his equipment and with capturing images.

In the image on the left, our colleague Andrés Domenech is pictured with Bkub Ōkawa, accompanied by plush versions of Pipimi and Popuko. On the right, there is a drawing of Popuko and Pipimi that our colleague gave to the author as a gift.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Official FicZone website, Anime News Network | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya
- **Images sourced from:** Anime News Network, Bkub Ōkawa's official Instagram account, Fandogamia, X. **Photographs taken by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es], Antonio Jiménez Fuentes

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